

Framing mathematics-related policy problems: Discourses linking school and district leaders to state policy

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The discourses reflected in policy structure how education is talked about, understood, and enacted in schools. This paper employs critical discourse analysis to explore how dominant discourses perpetuated by state policy penetrate school and district leaders' framing of mathematics-related policy problems. The analysis revealed that leaders employed neoliberal discourses, discourses of inclusion and diversity, and deficit discourses in ways that may inadvertently maintain educational inequality.

How a policy problem is *framed* is important because it assigns responsibility and legitimizes some solutions and not others (Benford & Snow, 2000). And, since leaders are most successful in influencing framing activity and the direction of work (Coburn, 2006; Penuel et al., 2013), this paper investigates how leaders frame problems in their schools and districts. To date, research on problem framing in education has focused on how frames are negotiated within a particular school or district. Attention to context has often been limited to school conditions, ignoring the influence of the broader sociopolitical environment. This is important, as research suggests national and state policy and parents and community members influence leaders' meaning making and policy responses (e.g., Turner, 2015). That is, leaders draw on broader discourses about education, including those from policy, in framing problems.

However, there is scarce research investigating these discourses—the language, practices, and identities reflected in talk about policy problems—especially with respect to mathematics education. Attending specifically to mathematics is important, as mathematics receives considerably more attention by policymakers (Spillane & Hopkins, 2013). As one of the two most tested subjects (U.S. Department of Education, 2015), mathematics is especially vulnerable to neoliberal discourses of standardization and accountability (Martin, 2013). Further, mathematics reflects and perpetuates broader racialized narratives about who is (and is not) good at mathematics (Martin, 2009), and by drawing on these discourses, leaders contribute to—or undermine—children's access to learning opportunities.

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Consistent with critical discourse studies, we argue that research on the discourses reflected in leaders' problem framings provide insights into the ways schools legitimize and reproduce inequity (Fairclough, 2015). To this end, we investigate how leaders in one U.S. school district frame mathematics-related policy problems. Specifically, we ask: What discourses are reflected in leaders' framing of mathematics-related problems? How do these discourses manifest or differ from those in state policy? How are these discourses employed in leaders' framing, and what purposes do they serve?

Conceptual framings

Frames are discursive devices actors invoke to strategically shape others' sensemaking and to mobilize them to take action (Benford & Snow, 2000). Frames identify conditions as problematic, assign responsibility, and privilege certain policy solutions (Stone, 2012). Because actors intentionally invoke frames that connect to the interests, values, and beliefs of those they hope to mobilize (Snow et al., 1986), school and district leaders hoping to define a certain condition as problematic or advance a particular solution might—with varying degrees of intentionality—employ dominant discourses. Therefore, this paper seeks to investigate the discourses leaders employ in their problem framing, and the purposes these discourses serve in identifying problems, casting blame, and legitimizing solutions.

Critical discourse analysis (CDA) argues that discourses are ideologically shaped by power relations (Fairclough, 2015). For school and district leaders then, their problem framing activity operates within broader sociopolitical contexts characterized by discourses competing for power. As such, leaders construct and negotiate frames that operate within and between discourses and the ideologies they embody, or at least those that are most powerful. Frames also take up and exert power through discourses. That is, frames that align or resonate with dominant ideologies are more likely to be taken up, serving to reproduce structures that sustain dominant interests. By bringing together CDA and framing, this study seeks to expose the dominant discourses employed in leaders' problem framing and how they empower or establish limits on practice.

Discourses in education

Under the guise of free-market capitalism, policies and reforms of the last several decades have increasingly focused on meeting the needs of the economy (Apple, 2006). Mathematics education in particular has served a neoliberal agenda through, for example, its commodification of learners and mathematics knowledge in service of military and national security (Martin, 2013). These discourses of economic productivity and efficiency have brought standardization and high-stakes accountability testing to the forefront (Au, 2016). Though such policies have been framed as supporting *all* students (Martin, 2003), this focus on accountability has been especially harmful for historically marginalized students (Davis & Martin, 2008).

Language like “all children” and “no child left behind” has been particularly powerful in uniting policymakers and educators around market-based school reforms (Lenhoff & Ulmer, 2016). While simplistically ideal, discourses of inclusion promote colorblindness (Martin, 2013) and marginalize the needs of historically underserved students (Martin, 2003). Inclusion has been linked to calls for diversity, which, more recently, has paired with neoliberal projects, including those that commodify non-white¹ racial identities, to focus exclusively on the positive learning outcomes for *all* students (Goldstein Hode & Meisenback, 2016). By connecting increased access to education for marginalized groups to goals that serve white interests, the neoliberal case for diversity promotes interest convergence (Bell, 1980) and detracts from more race-conscious practices that work to address past discrimination (Rhoads et al., 2005).

Implicit in accountability policies that fail to address structural racism and economic inequalities yet expect equality of outcomes (Darling-Hammond, 2007) are deficit discourses that construct students of color and low-income students and their families as the causes of academic failure (Valencia, 2010). As an alternative to a student deficit discourse, leaders may also draw upon a *teacher* deficit discourse, emphasizing the shortcomings of teachers and their instruction (Turner, 2015). However, like student deficit discourses, these reinforce problematic structures and deflect attention away from the district’s potential role in the reproduction of systemic racism and inequality.

Context and methods

Brookside School District (BSD, a pseudonym) is a rural school district in the U.S. state of Missouri. It serves about 1500 students, approximately 80% of whom are white and 80% identified as free or reduced lunch (an indicator of socioeconomic status)². In recent years, BSD has performed below the state average on standardized tests, with significant disparities between white and Black students. To address some of these concerns, in 2018, the district convened a Diversity Task Force (DTF), which was headed by the district superintendent and included community members. Since then, the state initiated a “Targeted Support and Improvement School Plan” for the middle school (grades 6–8) for the 2019–2022 school years, due to low achievement scores in mathematics and English language arts among Black students and students with individualized education plans. Missouri began identifying “Target” schools in 2018 as a response to the passage of the Every Student Succeeds Act (ESSA) in 2015.

Employing CDA, we examined the discourses reflected in leaders’ problem framing and in state policy. For the latter, we analyzed the Missouri Consolidated State Plan (2019) for meeting ESSA, paying particular attention to the policies for Targeted Support and Improvement Schools. We analyzed for leaders’ framings as emerging from three semi-

¹ We follow Gotanda (1991) in capitalizing Black and not capitalizing white.

² To protect confidentiality, we do not include additional demographic data.

structured interviews, conducted in 2020, with the middle school principal (Patty), the district superintendent (Stacy), and the district chief academic officer (Celia). These semi-structured interviews were approximately one hour long and covered a range of topics including their responsibilities, their perspectives on perceived challenges related to mathematics and equity, and the district's current equity initiatives.

Analysis began with reading through the interview transcripts to identify sections where leaders discussed math-related policy problems, including when they articulated the causes and solutions for such problems. These excerpts were then subjected to finer analysis where we coded for different discourses. We specifically attended to neoliberal discourses and discourses of inclusion and diversity because BSD leaders were facing pressures from the state to improve test scores, not just for historically marginalized students, but for all students. Initial analysis also revealed the prevalence of deficit discourses in leaders' talk. While we specifically attended to the aforementioned discourses, we also looked for others that might not fit these categories.

Then, we closely analyzed the discourses employed in leaders' framing, particularly attending to what Fairclough (2011) describes as *discourses* (ways of representing) and *style* (ways of being). Specifically, we examined the discourse or ways of representing by asking: What problems were presented? How were problems defined? Why are the problems significant? How were problems addressed? How was mathematics defined? We also examined style or ways of being: How did problems position students, families, and teachers? Who or what was the cause of the problem? Who were solutions for? How were students and their academic and mathematical abilities described? After, we looked for patterns across the different ways that discourses were employed in leaders' framing and the purposes they served. These emerged from the data as we compared and contrasted the ways these discourses were used to justify and legitimize problem frames, particularly those that served to maintain dominant ideologies and power relations. We took a similar approach in analyzing the state policy, particularly looking for continuities and contradictions between the policy and interviews.

Findings

Both Missouri policy and BSD leaders employed neoliberal discourses to identify problems centered on standardized test scores. Though Missouri policy drew upon structural inequity discourses to implicate a lack of access as the cause, this was undermined by deficit discourses. BSD leaders also employed deficit discourses, casting blame on students and their families, as well as teachers and their instruction. Both, however, ignored and deflected blame away from potentially problematic structures. Intertwined were also discourses of inclusion and diversity, which delegitimized solutions specifically for Black students. In the following sub-sections, we explain the various purposes these discourses served in leaders' problem framing.

Discourses identify and define problems

Missouri policy to ESSA employed neoliberal discourses to identify achievement-focused problems. In particular, Missouri's "first strategic goal is for all students to graduate from high school ready for college, career, and life," including "reducing by half the rate at which students fail to achieve proficiency" on state standardized tests (p. 17). Similar discourses were reflected in all BSD leaders' identification of achievement as an important problem. Stacy (the superintendent), for example, said that "academic achievement, of course, is always a focus and even outside of just state assessment data." Here, "of course" and "always" suggest that this problem is assumed and persistent, while "even outside" indicates that standardized test scores are accepted as a routine and legitimate measure of learning. Such language reflects the powerful hold neoliberal discourses have on the district and what Stacy considers problematic.

In addition to "improving outcomes for all students" (p. 2), Missouri tracks different subgroups to "close educational achievement gaps" (p. 10). These "subgroups" refer to different student populations, including, for example, white, Black, and Hispanic students, and not necessarily student groups that the state has identified as being historically underserved. By focusing on "all" students, Missouri policy draws on discourses of inclusion that reinforce a colorblind perspective and marginalize the needs of historically underserved students. Simultaneously, by focusing on achievement gaps, Missouri policy perpetuates the narrative that mathematics is a discipline in which those successful are white, middle-class (Martin et al., 2017).

Such problems and discourses were also reflected in BSD leaders' framing. For example, Patty (the middle school principal) explained that "our focus right now is, of course, to narrow the gap in skill achievement for our math students, but students overall, not just math but ELA as well, to help get us out of that Target status, but to get our kids where they need to be to be successful." Here, Patty suggested that the "gap" is important to address because of the state's labeling of the school as Target, and framed the problem centrally around students of color and their "achievement" on tests. However, reliance on test scores narrowly defines what counts as mathematics and, as Adiredja and Louie (2020) have argued, fails to acknowledge students' out-of-school knowledge. And by framing the achievement of students of color against that of white students, Patty participated in "gap-gazing" (Gutiérrez, 2008) that perpetuates the narrative of Black students as underperforming (Martin et al., 2017).

Discourses assign (and deflect) blame

Discourses not only identify and define problems, they also assign blame. Employing structural inequity discourses, which focus on the role of inequitable social structures in student achievement (Bertrand et al., 2015), Missouri policy attributed the cause of poor achievement to a lack of access. For example, to support the goal that all Missouri students graduate college and career ready is "access, opportunity, equity," which ensures that "best practices and quality programs must be available to every child from preschool through postsecondary" (p. 6). Thus, Missouri policy implies that the cause of poor achievement is

that not “every” student is afforded access to quality schools and opportunities. Little attention, however, is given to the structural and institutional forces that create and maintain such inequities in access.

Further, the structural inequity discourses employed in Missouri policy were weakened alongside the deficit discourses also present. The Target Schools policy defines schools as not meeting quality indicators by identifying those with “consistently underperforming subgroups” (p. 30). Rather than, for example, positioning students as not being afforded access to quality educational opportunities, students were instead described as “chronically low-performing” (p. 29). By invoking a disease metaphor (Stone, 2012), Missouri policy naturalizes students as academically unsuccessful and centers students’ perceived internal deficits as the cause for poor achievement.

BSD leaders also ignored problematic structures when drawing on deficit discourses that cast blame on students and their families. Patty, for example, explained that Black students’ test scores have been low because “I think some of that is just, not just, but is socioeconomic-based in our community. We’ve lost so much industry here. Our SES is much lower than it used to be.” More specifically, she explained that:

Because what I see with our Black students in particular is that they, if the students that come out of pretty strong foundational homes, whatever that structure looks like, they’ve got a good home base tend to see the value in math, or they have an intrinsic interest in math, and those are the ones that are successful.

By implying that the problem could be connected to an economic depression in the broader community, Patty framed the problem around issues of class instead of race. She, however, did not give a justification for why poverty might more negatively affect Black students than white students (nor did any other leader who framed the problem in a similar way). Patty then went on to dismiss these structural arguments by suggesting that Black students are not successful in mathematics because they either are not intrinsically interested or do not come from a “strong foundational” home. By drawing on deficit discourses, Patty not only attributed the cause of the problem to Black students and their families, but also obscured institutional racism (Martin, 2013) and other structural issues, such as a lack of jobs in the community.

In addition to placing blame on students and their families, leaders also attributed responsibility to teachers. Celia (the chief academic officer), for example, explained that Black students’ test scores are low because:

Teachers have really focused on more of a traditional approach and not really trying to see and meet the needs of every, you know. This way doesn’t always work for kids and how can we kind of change our teaching or instruction to kind of meet those needs...Our elementary teachers are not really comfortable with math.

Celia explained that teachers’ “traditional” instruction and lack of mathematics content knowledge do not meet students’ needs. By focusing on instructional practices, she, on the one hand, places responsibility for the problem within the institution (i.e., on teachers’ instruction). On the other hand, by only focusing on teachers and teaching, Celia ignored

the possibility of her own and others' complicity and deflected responsibility for the problem by obscuring what role the district might be playing in perpetuating racial inequality (Turner, 2015). Intertwined in the teacher-deficit discourses are also discourses of inclusion. By attending to teaching practices that "meet the needs of every" student, Celia ignored why teachers' current instruction more negatively affects Black students than white students and precludes any solutions that would specifically meet the needs of Black students.

Discourses (de)legitimize solutions

Finally, discourses legitimize some solutions and not others. To ensure that "all children have equitable access to opportunities that prepare them for success in school and in life" (Missouri Department of Elementary & Secondary Education, 2019, p. 6), Missouri policy offered accountability-focused solutions. In particular, the state administers reports with achievement data, and "these reports can and do drive improvement for all students, helping to close educational achievement gaps" (p. 10). That is, the Target Schools policy identifies schools with "chronically low-performing subgroups" (p. 29) and compels them to improve, through carrots-and-sticks accountability, so that "all" students achieve. While such policies might be "successful" in incentivizing schools to focus on outcomes, which indeed are the problems BSD leaders identified, Missouri gives little guidance on how schools can actually improve achievement, particularly for their historically marginalized students.

BSD leaders took up this charge by convening a Diversity Task Force (DTF) with the local community, whose main initiative has been a mentoring program. Originally, the mentoring program was designed specifically for Black students, but this resulted in community backlash from (mostly) white parents. Celia explained that "I think just in our community. I think we have to kind of open it up to everybody [...] We tried to kind of target that and bringing in some speakers and things and it didn't seem to go over as well." In response, BSD leaders and the DTF decided to "open it up" by using chronic attendance as a qualifying criterion. Stacy explained that:

We're going to use chronic attendance as our qualifying characteristic which we just decided, kind of really solidifying that because we don't want to be so exclusive that we're not including other students just because they're not Black or just because they're not fitting what we say, you know, this one area. And so we know that chronic attendance is related to academics, is related to behavior, is related to parent engagement. And so all of the students that we feel that we could reach and touch fit that mold and the likelihood that we're going to reach students that are a minority population is significant we feel.

Here, Stacy explained that the DTF's mentoring program originally targeted Black students, one of the subgroups the state alerted them to, but in response to community backlash, retreated to discourses of inclusion, employing some of the very same language Missouri policy provided about attendance. In another part of the interview, Stacy explained that chronic attendance (absenteeism) refers to a state indicator for students that miss more than 10% of school days. Indeed, the 90/90 attendance principle—"90 percent of the students must be in attendance 90 percent of the time" (p. 7)—is one of the performance indicators for

the School Improvement Program. This suggests that Stacy, and the district, used state policy to target most of their Black students without being “exclusive.”

Though this problem framing is well-intentioned, by employing discourses of inclusion, including those from Missouri policy, solutions originally focused on Black students’ learning were translated into that of all students. And, by connecting achievement to attendance, and attendance to student behavior and parent involvement, Stacy suggested that Black students are not successful in mathematics because they are not well behaved and have disengaged parents. This framing, reflecting both deficit discourses and discourses of inclusion, materialized into a mentoring event where a “diverse” set of speakers—a white, female alumna and female high school student of color—presented “to any middle school student” about work ethic.

Discussion

Missouri policy employed neoliberal discourses to identify achievement problems and accountability solutions to address a lack of access. Such structural inequity discourses were, however, undermined by deficit discourses that positioned students as underperforming and the cause of poor achievement. Simultaneously, discourses of inclusion and diversity centered the importance of “all” students achieving, which marginalized the needs of those historically underserved. As seen in this analysis, these broader discourses make their way into leaders’ problem framing activity, with varying levels of intentionality. On the one hand, leaders seemed to be fairly aware of the hold neoliberal discourses had on what they considered problematic. Such discourses, however, were difficult to interrupt, especially as there were few alternative discourses available to identify different problems, including, for example, those related to equity beyond disparities in achievement. On the other hand, leaders seemed to be unintentionally employing deficit discourses, yet these still crept in. Meanwhile, discourses of inclusion were, at times, strategically invoked, especially because they held currency in the community, as was the case of using chronic absenteeism to target Black students while avoiding being “exclusive.”

CDA explains that because discourses are linked to the distribution of resources (Gee, 2014), those reflected in leaders’ problem framing have the potential to transform or maintain power relations. More common in this analysis were discourses that appeared to uphold, or at least not challenge, educational inequities. For example, while Missouri policy did implicate inequitable access, it did not explicitly discuss the role of structural and institutional forces in maintaining said inequities. Without such discourses available to be taken up, BSD leaders’ problem framing ignored solutions that would address any problematic structures. Related, discourses of inclusion and diversity legitimized an “inclusive” mentoring program, which manifested in social practice as a case of interest convergence (Bell, 1980) where Black students were only afforded social goods (mentoring) if white students were as well. Despite wanting to improve mathematics instruction for Black students, discourses crept into BSD leaders’ problem framing in ways that maintained dominant interests.

An important implication here is that the discourses reflected in state and national policies can influence how local leaders frame policy problems. Such discourses limit or expand how problems are defined and what solutions are possible, serving to maintain or challenge inequality. Critical awareness of the discourses available and powerful in the broader sociopolitical environment, and the implications they have for policy solutions and how students are positioned, may allow leaders to more intentionally address educational inequalities and improve mathematics teaching for students, especially those historically marginalized. However, because many of these discourses are perpetuated by broader state and federal policies, advancing equity in mathematics education must necessarily involve change at an institutional level.

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